

Use of Vegetation Indices for Monitoring Forest Cover in a Conservation Unit in the Far West of the State of Acre

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Keywords: Geotechnologies, Remote Sensing, Vegetation Indices, EVI, NDVI, NDWI, Sentinel-2.

The western region of Acre, characterized by its natural beauty and ecological significance, faces the threat of unregulated deforestation, compromising the integrity of local ecosystems (Marinelli et al., 2008). The creation of protected areas aims to preserve these environments and these unique species (BNDES, 2020). Geotechnologies, such as remote sensing and vegetation indices, are precise for monitoring and assessing changes in vegetation cover, providing precise data for decision-making (Gomes Barbosa et al., 2021; Rosendo, 2015). The monitoring project of ARIE Japiim Pentecoste employs these technologies conservation and sustainable management of the area.

The research was conducted in ARIE Japiim Pentecoste, a conservation unit located in the municipalities of Cruzeiro do Sul and Mâncio Lima, Acre, covering an area of 25,750.9762 hectares. The predominant vegetation includes Alluvial Ombrophilous Forest and Terra Firme Forest, with a humid tropical climate, temperatures ranging between 24,6° and 25,2°, and annual precipitation above 2000mm (ACRE, 2014). The relief is characterized by erosion and sedimentary lithologies, with altitudes between 110 and 270 meters (ACRE, 2014).

Platforms such as MapBiomias and Google Earth Engine were used for land use and cover analysis, allowing access to satellite images and climatic data. Sentinel-2 images from 2018 and 2022 were processed to evaluate vegetation using NDVI and EVI indices, wish measure vegetation health (Matsushita et al., 2007; Allen et al., 2002; Silva et al., 2017).

The results indicated significant seasonal variation in vegetation indices over the years. The EVI from Sentinel-2 (figure 1) showed a decreasing trend starting in 2022, suggesting a possible change in forest cover. The NDVI from Landsat-8 (graphic 1) displayed a similar pattern with decreased values starting in 2019. The seasonal dynamics were also assessed using the NDWI (graphic 2), which indicated significant variation in the presence of water bodies over the studied period. Comparisons between different years (figure 2) revealed notable changes in vegetation cover and water conditions in the region, highlighting the importance of continuous monitoring to understand environmental transformation.

Figure 1 - Indices Enhanced Vegetation Index

comparing the satellites Landsat-8 e Sentinel-2
Fonte: the author, 2024.

Grafic 1 - Values Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (Landsat-8).

Grafic 2 – Values Normalized Difference Water Index (Landsat-8).

Figure 2 - Indices Normalized Difference Water Index comparing the years of 2021 and 2022.

The study of ARIE Japiim Pentecoste underscores the critical role of geotechnologies in monitoring and managing the health of ecosystems. The observed seasonal and temporal variation in vegetation indices, such as NDVI and EVI, reflect significant changes in forest cover and environmental conditions. The trend of decreasing EVI from Sentinel-2 and the similar decline in

NDVI from Landsat-8 highlight the potential shifts in the region's forest cover that warrant further investigation. Additionally, using NDWI to track changes in water bodies further emphasizes the dynamic nature of the environment.

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